

ELEMENT-BY-ELEMENT RELIABILITY CALCULATION METHOD WITH THE COMPONENTS COMPLEXITY COEFFICIENTS OF THE PRODUCT

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***Abstract.** The theoretical aspects of the reliability theory are researched; the main reliability calculation methods (statistical and predicted) are analyzed; the calculation of the complexity coefficients for the functional definite components of the product is proposed; an element-by-element method of calculation is suggested, taking into account the complexity coefficients of certain functional components of the product and an assessment of the dependence of the probability of failure-free operation of the product as a whole on the probability of failure-free operation of its individual structural elements. The calculation of fault-free operation of the product was carried out, considering the operating modes of the component block elements. The coefficient method and the method with the assessment of the real loads of the elements are counted, based on the availability of complete information about the object and its operating conditions. Correction coefficients regarding the operating conditions of the product are taken into account, which are clear indicators of such factors as the temperature of the surrounding environment, mechanical loads, humidity and atmospheric pressure, etc. Based on the analysis, using the full probability formula considering the conditional probabilities of failure-free*

operation of the product components, it is proposed to determine the probability of product failure depending on the probability of failure of a certain definite component. As a result, the proposed method estimated the probability that this event occurred due to the failure of a certain component, the probability of failure of which is higher than that of others. It is suggested to estimate the probability of the occurrence of such an event using the Bayes formula. Methods of increasing reliability are analyzed, one of which is redundancy for product elements with the lowest probability of failure-free operation. It is emphasized that there are cases when it is necessary to ensure the appropriate value of reliability in the presence of restrictions on mass, energy consumption, dimensions, and cost of the system. In such cases, the optimal number of redundancy areas is established, at which the probability of system failure is minimal, and such a number of redundant elements is determined to ensure the maximum possible value of the system reliability indicator while meeting all the given restrictions.

Keywords: *reliability theory, probability of faultless work, instantaneous failure rate, complexity coefficient, correction coefficient, conditional probability of failures, methods of increasing reliability, redundancy.*

Formulation of the problem. In the conditions of modern production, the enterprise in its work, sooner or later, will certainly face competition from enterprises selling similar products. That is why the key to the successful functioning of the enterprise is its competitiveness [6]. In the manufacturing of modern products, quality is considered as the main factor. In most cases, ensuring reliability of the product, as one of the most significant quality indicators, is of primary importance and priority before ensuring minimum dimensions, weight and cost. Ukraine is actively integrating into world civilizational processes. Ukraine's entry into the international competitive space strengthens the role of quality in the competitiveness of products on world markets.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The main concepts of reliability are determined by the state standards of Ukraine: DSTU 2860-94 Reliability of equipment. Terms and definitions., DSTU 2861-94 Reliability of equipment. Reliability analysis. Basic provisions., DSTU 2862-94 Reliability of equipment. Methods of calculating reliability indicators. General requirements. Theoretical and practical studies of reliability theory were widely observed in the works of Burlakov V.I., Semenov A.A., Vasylevsky O.M., Korenivska O.L., Benedytsky V.B., Kustov V.F., Nechyporenko O.M. ., Vyshnivsky V.V., Pavlyuk O.M., M.O. Medykovsky, as well as in the works of foreign scientists Norman Paskoe, Aven Terrier, Patrick O'Conner, Andre Kleiner and other leading ukrainian and foreign scientists.

The purpose and objectives of the article. Analyze the existing reliability calculation methods and propose an element-by-element predicted method of reliability calculation, depending on the coefficients indicating the component complexity of particular components of the product.

Main matter presenting. Products of modern technology usually have high functional complexity. At the same time, the primary importance, in the conditions of increasing complexity and saturation of modern technique with functional capabilities, belongs to ensuring reliability. At all stages of the product's functioning, reliability is its most important property and requires constant attention, control and forecasting. Reliability depends on many factors, both internal, which relate exclusively to the device itself, and external, which depend on the conditions of operation and storage. The internal factors affecting the reliability of the product include: the quality of designing, manufacture and assembly of the device, as well as the quality of the materials and components that are used. To the external – stable functioning of the product under proper operating conditions and saving of working capacity under proper storage conditions of the product. The high reliability of the product can be ensured by the sum of the necessary measures which are performed at all stages of development, production and operation. The leading place in this process

belongs to the design stage, where the main indicators of product reliability are defined, selected and calculated. Project designers of modern equipment should strive for extremely high reliability, considering all possible functional situations. When designing, they ensure the fulfillment of the requirements necessary for any product: tactical and technical characteristics, optimal design, manufacturability, reduction of cost and time for design, etc. Designers should choose optimal solutions for high reliability and obtaining the necessary technical characteristics. The modern regulatory base of Ukraine for reliability issues is based on DSTU 2860.94 "Reliability of equipment. Terms and definitions." According to DSTU, reliability is defined as *"the ability of an object to save over time, within the established limits, the values of all parameters that characterize the ability to perform the necessary functions in the specified modes and conditions of use, maintenance, repairs, storage and transportation"* [1].

Reliability of technical objects is a complex property that combines the concepts of four properties: failure-free operation, durability, repair ability, storage ability. Failure-free operation indicators: probability of failure-free operation, failure intensity, average working time before failure. Durability indicators: average service life, average service life before write-off, gamma-percentage service life, average service life before average (capital) repair, average service life between average (capital) repairs, assigned resource, average resource, gamma-percentage resource, average resource between average (capital) repairs, average resource before write-off, average resource before average (capital) repairs. Indicators of maintainability: recovery probability, average recovery time, recovery intensity. Shelf life indicators: average shelf life and gamma-percent shelf life. Reliability indicators make it possible to carry out calculation and analytical evaluation of quantitative characteristics of individual properties when choosing various schematic and structural options of equipment (objects) during their development, testing and operation [7].

One of the main indicators of the reliability of technical objects is the probability of fault-free operation $P(t)$ over a period of time. This is the probability that, under certain operating conditions, failure will not occur within a given period of operation. By the source of information there are analytical methods of reliability calculation (evaluative calculation) and methods based on operating data (statistical calculation). According to the completeness of the calculation and the information obtained as a result of this calculation, the methods are divided into complete and approximate. Usually, the probability of failure-free operation is determined by statistical data on failures obtained during reliability testing of a batch of products, and is estimated by the expression:

$$P(t) = \frac{V-v(t)}{V},$$

where V is the number of products in the batch for testing; $v(t)$ is the number of products that failed during the time interval t .

Often, instead of the probability of failure-free operation $P(t)$, the characteristic of the probability of failure $Q(t)$ is used, an indicator that under certain operating conditions at least one failure will occur in a given time interval. The failure-free operation and the failure probability are incompatible and opposite events, therefore

$$Q(t) = 1 - P(t).$$

According to the statistical data of the tests, the probability of failure can be determined by the expression:

$$Q(t) = \frac{v(t)}{V}.$$

Approximate methods are used at the design stage. In order to check the compliance of the requirements of the technical task with the reliability indicators and to compare different versions for the implementation of the project, preliminary predicted calculations of the reliability indicators are performed.

It is proposed an element-by-element method of calculation, considering the complexity coefficients of definite functional components of the product and

assessing the dependence of the probability of failure-free operation of the product as a whole on the probability of failure-free operation of its specific structural elements.

Let the product consist of n structural elements of the components of the product according to the structural or functional scheme connected in consequent serie, and the failure of one of them will lead to the failure of the product as a whole. Each of these constituent units of product has a different number of working components in its composition, which affect the stable operation of the node and ensure that it fulfills the necessary functional load. Designers determine the total number of such components for the product, mechanical (reducers, springs, gears, clutches, pulleys, etc.) and electronic (microcontrollers, amplifiers, transistors, resonators, relays, sensors, chokes, etc.) that affect the proper operation of the device and can break down. Let k denote the total number of working elements for the product and j the number of such elements for a separate block. Then the ratio

$$r = \frac{j}{k}$$

is a coefficient that indicates the complexity, saturation of working elements and the vulnerability of not obtaining the proper characteristics in case of failure for a certain component unit in relation to the entire product. Thus, the corresponding complexity coefficients $r_1, r_2, r_3, \dots, r_n$ are determined for n structural elements. Based on the definition of the coefficient, it is possible to write

$$\sum_{i=1}^n r_i = 1.$$

The next step is to calculate the probability of failure-free operation for all n blocks. A complete calculation of fault-free operation involves taking into account the operating modes of the component block elements. Depending on the completeness of such consideration, a coefficient method and a method with an assessment of the real loads of the elements are distinguished. All calculation methods are based on the availability of complete information about the object and its operating conditions. A necessary condition for obtaining more accurate reliability

characteristics in calculations is an assessment of the intensity of element failures, taking into account all external influencing factors. The most significant factors are the temperature of the surrounding environment, mechanical loads, humidity and atmospheric pressure, etc. Correction coefficients that take these factors into account are calculated by the ratio of the intensity of failures of elements of the i -th group λ_i , under the given operating conditions, to the intensity of failures of some main element λ_0 , the quantitative characteristics of which are reliably known under fairly close operating conditions:

$$K_i = \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_0}.$$

Then, the intensity of element failures, considering the correction coefficients for the operating conditions of the product, is determined by the formula:

$$\varphi = \lambda_0 \sum_{i=1}^n m_i K_i$$

where m_i is the number of working elements in the block, K_i is the corresponding correction coefficient of the external factor. The value of the nominal intensity of failures λ_0 and correction factors are selected for each working element of the block from the reference data provided by the manufacturer of this component. Based on the data on the intensity of failures, the probability of failure-free operation of the unit during a certain period of operation t_p is calculated, which is subjected to the exponential law of the distribution of failures

$$P(t) = e^{-\varphi t_p},$$

where e is a fundamental mathematical constant that is the basis of natural logarithms, t_p is the time of normal operation of the product for a certain period of time. Accordingly, the probability of failure can be determined as

$$Q(t) = 1 - e^{-\varphi t_p}.$$

Having calculated the probabilities of failure-free operation or failure probabilities for product blocks, we can note that these data directly depend on the complexity of the block, the saturation of a definite block with working elements that

are likely to fail. Thus, such block-by-block probabilities of failure-free operation or failure probabilities can be considered conditional probabilities $P(\varphi|r)$ or $Q(\varphi|r)$ depending on the corresponding complexity factors for each of the product blocks. So, according to the formula of total probability for a product consisting of n functional blocks, it is possible to write

$$P(\varphi) = \sum_{i=1}^n P(r_i) P(\varphi|r_i),$$

where $P(\varphi)$ is the probability of failure-free operation of the product depending on the intensity of failures, $P(r_i) = r_i$ is the complexity factor of the i -th block, depending on the complexity of the entire product, which is taken as 1.

As a result, the proposed method, considering the case of failure of the entire product, in the case of consequent connection of functional elements, when the failure of one element leads to the failure of the product as a whole, it is possible to estimate the probability that this event occurred from for the failure of a certain component, the probability of failure of which is higher than that of others. An estimate of the probability of occurrence of such an event as the failure of the entire product $Q(r_j|\varphi)$, due to a certain component unit, can be calculated using the Bayes formula:

$$Q(r_j|\varphi) = 1 - \frac{P(r_j)P(\varphi|r_j)}{\sum_{i=1}^n P(r_i)P(\varphi|r_i)},$$

where $P(r_j) = r_j$ is the complexity factor of a separate block, $P(\varphi|r_j)$ is the conditional probability of the product's failure-free operation depending on the complexity factor.

Having received calculations of the probability of failure of the product depending on the failure of one of its components, designers apply methods of increasing reliability for elements with the highest probability of failure, among which structural reservation is the main one. Reservation is the use of additional redundant elements in order to preserve the operational state of the object in case of failure of one or more of its elements [5]. The reserve element is turned on in parallel

with the main one. One main element can be connected to several backup elements. A reasonable number of reserve elements is determined by the level of reliability, which should be ensured, by costs of reservation, by mass-dimensional indicators, etc. According to the method of switching-on of the reserve, there is a distinction between: passive (a type of reserve in which the failure of one or more objects does not affect its operation) and active reserve (a type of reserve in which, when an element fails, the structure of the circuit is rearranged) [8].

Often, there are cases when it is necessary to ensure the appropriate level of reliability in the presence of restrictions on mass, energy consumption, dimensions, and cost of the system. In this case, the first priority is to establish the optimal number of reservation areas, at which the probability of system failure is minimal, and determine such a number of backup elements that the maximum possible value of the system reliability indicator is ensured while meeting all the given restrictions.

Therefore, when designing products of modern technique, designers should strive for maximum reliability, realizing that stable failure-free operation, appropriate tactical and technical indicators, competitiveness of the product, and sometimes even the life of the consumer depend on this.

Conclusions and perspectives for further researches. As a result of the conducted analysis and research, the use of special coefficients of complexity of particular component products for reliability calculations is justified. On the basis of conditional probabilities and the formula of total probability, the probability of failure of the device is determined, depending on the number of working elements in the functional unit. When designing a product, it is possible to calculate the probability of failure-free operation and to estimate the share of each structural element in a possible device failure using the Bayes formula.

Summarizing the all above, we can conclude that at the designing stage, the analysis and determination of product reliability is a comprehensive event and includes:

- search, analysis and generalization of information on all factors affecting product reliability;
- designing of structural and functional schemes considering the providing of tactical and technical characteristics, quality and reliability of the product;
- search for optimal technical solutions, selection of components and materials that would contribute to the stable and reliable operation of the device;
- designing of parts, nodes, blocks and assembly units with quality and reliability assurance;
- preliminary calculation of complexity coefficients, correction coefficients and probabilities of failure-free operation or probabilities of failures of nodes, blocks, assembly units and the device as a whole;
- making the changes and additions to the structural, functional schemes and construction of nodes, blocks, assembly units with providing a high probability of failure, using methods of increasing reliability;
- the final calculation of the reliability of the product, the probability of failure-free operation, the probability of failures and making a decision on the introduction into production.

As a conclusion, it can be noted that the concepts of quality and reliability are closely related and characterize the ability of the device to be used as assigned, its stable operation and compliance with all the established requirements of the technical documentation.

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